

Oxidative coupling of coumarin compounds with fuming sulphuric acid : 4,4'-bicumarinyls as axially chiral compounds

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3-Hydroxycoumarin (1) and 3-aminocoumarin (4) underwent oxidative dimerisation on reaction with hot fuming sulphuric acid to furnish 3,3'-dihydroxy-4,4'-bicumarinyl (2) and 3,3'-diamino-4,4'-bicumarinyl (5) respectively in apparently non-oxidative reaction conditions. On reaction with malic acid in fuming sulphuric acid 1 produced 2 only whereas 4 produced mixture of 5 and fumaric acid *N*-(3-coumarinyl)monoamide (6). 2 reacted with Lawesson's reagent to furnish 3,3'-dihydroxy-4,4'-bi(benzo[*b*]pyran)-2,2'-dithione (3). ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR studies of 2, 3 and 5 revealed elaborate anisotropic effect of one coumarin ring of the axially chiral compound on the other coumarin unit.

The oxidative coupling of phenols to dimeric products, bisphenols, is a useful procedure which has found extensive application in chemical analysis. The bio-mimetic coupling reaction appears to involve initial oxidation of the phenol by loss of one electron giving rise to an aryloxy radical which then undergoes quick dimerisation¹, such intermediate radicals have been detected in a number of cases by ESR spectroscopy. The most successful oxidants are ones which are generally considered to act by one electron transfer. 2-Naphthol undergoes oxidative coupling reaction with hot aqueous ferric chloride to produce 2,2'-dihydroxy-1,1'-binaphthyl² in a very good yield. Being an active Friedel-Crafts catalyst, this reagent has a limited scope and is liable to bring about additional unwanted transformation. Alkaline potassium ferricyanide³, although used in a number of cases, has the disadvantage of tendering possible over-oxidation of the initially formed bisphenol to the quinone. Triacetylacetonatemanaganese(II) and phosphomolybdic acid on silica gel support are candidates for oxidation of phenols to bisphenols^{4,5}. In a different approach, 2,2'-diamino-1,1'-binaphthyl⁶ was synthesized by *ortho*-semidine rearrangement of *N,N'*-bi-(2-naphthyl)hydrazine with antimonyl pentafluoride-hydrogen fluoride-sulphur dioxide in sulphuryl chlorofluoride at -78°.

During the last two decades, based on the pioneering efforts of Cram and his coworkers⁷, optically active 1,1'-binaphthyl compounds such as chiral reagent exemplified by Naylor's BINAP-H^{8a,8b} having axial chirality have been recognized to be effective constituents of many asymmetric reagents⁸. Although most of the successful attempts of resolution of these axially dissymmetric aromatic molecules

used chemical methods⁹, microbial resolution of 2,2'-dihydroxy-1,1'-binaphthyl via selective hydrolysis of its dicarboxylic ester is also reported¹⁰. Optical resolution of 10,10'-dihydroxy-9,9'-biphenanthryl has been achieved by HPLC with a column packed with (+)polytriphenylmethyl methacrylate¹¹.

We wish to report here a synthesis of 3,3'-di(hydroxy/amino)-4,4'-bicumarinyl compounds by way of oxidative dimerisation of 3-(hydroxy/amino)coumarin compounds in essentially non-radical encouraging reaction conditions using hot fuming sulphuric acid and the queer nuclear magnetic resonance features of these compounds.

4-Hydroxycoumarin undergoes Pechmann condensation with malic acid and sulphuric acid to produce pyrano[3,2-*c*]benzopyran-2,5-dione¹². The hydroxy group of 3-hydroxycoumarin (1) is less reactive than that of 4-hydroxycoumarin¹³ and a difference of behaviour of 3-hydroxycoumarin (1) under Pechmann condensation condition with malic acid and sulphuric acid is expected. When 1 was heated with either (a) malic acid and 20% fuming sulphuric acid for 5 h on steam bath, or (b) 20% fuming sulphuric acid only on steam bath for 5 h, 3,3'-dihydroxy-4,4'-bicumarinyl (2) was isolated in either case; malic acid did not enter into reaction with 1 although under the condition of the reaction malic acid should undergo decarboxylation to produce highly reactive formylacetic acid¹². Instead, possible oxidation of 1 in an ionic mechanism is induced by fuming sulphuric acid furnishing the dimeric product 2 (Scheme 1); NMR features of 2 has been discussed (*vide infra*). Since positive FAB-MS (glycerol as matrix) of 2 furnished low intensity peak at 323 (M⁺ + 1), 2

was reacted with Lawesson's reagent¹⁴ in refluxing toluene for 2 h to get 3,3'-dihydroxy-4,4'-bis(benzo[*b*]pyran)-2,2'-dithione (**3**). The positive FAB-MS of **3** in a matrix of *m*-nitrobenzyl alcohol containing sodium chloride offered very strong peak at *m/z* 377 ($M + Na^+$) corresponding to the M^+ at 354 and thus extending a support for the dimeric structure of **3**.

3-Aminocoumarin¹³ (**4**), on heating with 20% fuming sulphuric acid on steam bath for 5 h, similarly furnished the dimeric oxidation product 3,3'-diamino-4,4'-bicyoumarinyl (**5**) in 49.1% yield. On the other hand, reaction of **4** with malic acid and 20% fuming sulphuric acid on steam bath for 5 h furnished a mixture of **5** and fumaric acid *N*-(coumarinyl)monoamide (**6**) which were separated and identified (Scheme 1). The difference in the behaviour of 3-hydroxycoumarin (**1**) and 3-aminocoumarin (**4**) towards malic acid in the presence of hot fuming sulphuric acid is reconcilable in terms of much higher nucleophilicity of the 3-amino moiety of **4** compared to that of 3-hydroxy group

Scheme 1. Reagents and reaction conditions : (i) 20% f. H_2SO_4 , 100°; (ii) malic acid + 20% f. H_2SO_4 , 100°, (iii) Lawesson's reagent, toluene, Δ ; (iv) 20% f. H_2SO_4 , 100°; (v) malic acid + 20% f. H_2SO_4 , 100°.

of **1**. As such, amino group of **4** initially condensed with one COOH group of malic acid followed by dehydration of the $CH_2CH(OH)$ moiety under hot and strongly acidic condition to the *E*-vinyl moiety; this mode of reaction of malic acid in a hot sulphuric acid condition is in contradiction with regular decarbonylation feature of malic acid under similar reaction condition. **6** shows strong carbonyl absorption at 1730 and 1630 cm^{-1} and a broad absorption at 3100–3450 cm^{-1} in its IR spectrum. In its 1H NMR spectrum, it shows two one-proton doublets at δ 5.81 and 6.20 with a coupling constant value of 13.2 Hz corresponding to the presence of *E*-vinyl moiety in **6**. In its ^{13}C NMR spectrum, the two vinylic carbons appear at δ 129.36 and 139.53

whereas the methine carbons of the coumarin ring appear at δ 123.68, 128.78, 124.84, 127.76 and 115.76 for C-4, C-5, C-6, C-7 and C-8 respectively. Quaternary carbon signals appear at δ 157.21, 125.74, 119.92 and 149.95 for C-2, C-3, C-4a and C-8a of the coumarin ring, the two carbonyl carbons of the monoamido fumaric moiety appear at δ 165.52 and 169.49. **6**, on attempted ring closure with refluxing trifluoroacetic acid, underwent cleavage of the amide bond to produce 3-aminocoumarin (**4**).

Nuclear magnetic resonance feature :

Molecules of **2**, **3** and **5** would show atropisomerism where the two benzopyran rings connected along C4-C4' would exist in mutually perpendicular fashion and one benzopyran ring would be under the anisotropic influence of the other. Anisotropic influence of one aromatic ring on the protons of another aromatic ring has been shown with 7-methoxy-5,6-dimethyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-1-naphthoyl *N*-[1-(4-*H*/nitrophenyl)ethyl]amide¹⁵ where the H-8 of the naphthalene ring has been shielded to the extent of ~ 0.7 ppm by the anisotropic influence of the phenyl ring. The anisotropic shielding is strongest as expected on the H-5 of **2**, **3** and **5** where the signals appear as singlets at δ 6.95, 6.98 and 6.72 respectively. For 3,3'-diamino-4,4'-biphenyl (**5**), the effect is very elaborate and H-6/H-6', H-7/H-7' and H-8/H-8' protons appear as doublet (J 1.9 Hz), double-doublet (J 1.9 Hz and 8.4 Hz) and doublet (J 8.4 Hz) respectively with the extent of spin-spin coupling increasing as the corresponding protons become more distant from the source of anisotropy. For 3,3'-dihydroxy-4,4'-bicyoumarinyl (**2**), the H-6/H-6' protons appear as singlet and only H-7/H-7' and H-8/H-8' protons can undergo spin-spin coupling, to appear as doublets with J 5.6 Hz. The same feature is observed by **3**, where H-6/H-6' protons appear as singlet and only H-7/H-7' and H-8/H-8' protons appear as doublets with J 6.9 Hz. Anisotropic shielding has also been established in terms of ^{13}C NMR signals; in case of 2,2'-dihydroxy-1,1'-biphenanthryl the shielding is prominent with C-1/C-1', and C-10/C-10' signals and in case of 7,7'-dimethoxy-8,8'-biphenanthryl with C-8, C-8' and C-9, C-9' signals⁵; in the same report, the chemical shift values for C-8/C-8' of 2,2'-dihydroxy-1,1'-binaphthyl has been shown to be as low as δ 123.9 as a result of such anisotropic influence. For **2**, **3** and **5**, anisotropic influence has been uniformly observed on C-5/C-5', C-6/C-6' and C-7/C-7', as evident from the ^{13}C -chemical shift values, compared with the ^{13}C -chemical shift values of the corresponding carbons of the monomer viz. 3-hydroxycoumarin (**1**), 3-hydroxybenzo[*b*]pyran-2-thione (**3**) and 3-aminocoumarin (**4**) respectively. On the other hand, the ^{13}C NMR signals for C-4/C-4' carbons of **2**, **3** and **5** revealed that these carbons have enjoyed anisotro-

Table 1. Comparison of ^{13}C NMR chemical shift values in ppm downfield from TMS of **1**, **3** and **5** with those of the corresponding monomer

Compd.	C-2	C-3	C-4	C-5	C-6	C-7	C-8	C-4a	C-8a
2	158.4	147.5	141.7	113.0	121.9	125.6	114.6	120.7	148.3
3-Hydroxycoumarin	158.7	141.8	115.2	126.5	124.7	127.7	115.7	120.8	149.3
3	161.4	–	126.6	113.5	132.4	132.5	113.7	124.4	–
3-Hydroxybenzo[b]pyran-2-thione	192.7	152.9	108.5	128.8	122.2	126.8	116.3	122.2	148.38
5	158.7	144.9	134.0	107.8	122.0	123.1	114.9	120.8	147.8
3-Aminocoumarin	158.6	133.25	107.7	124.7	124.4	125.3	115.4	121.8	147.9

pic deshielding, over and above the regular deshielding offered by the aromatic substituent in the dimeric form. A comparison of the ^{13}C NMR chemical shift values in ppm of **2**, **3** and **5** with those of the monomer is given in Table 1.

Experimental

The melting points are uncorrected. IR spectra were taken as KBr pellets on a Perkin-Elmer 782 spectrophotometer and UV spectra of ethanolic solutions of the compounds were recorded on a Hitachi U-200 spectrophotometer. The ^1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR spectra of the compounds were run on a Bruker AM-300L instrument operating at 300 MHz and 75.4 MHz respectively in $\text{DMSO}-d_6$ solutions. Petrol refers to one with boiling range 60–80°.

3,3'-Dihydroxy-4,4'-bicoumarinyl (**2**):

3-Hydroxycoumarin (**1**) (3.4 g, 20.98 mmol) was added slowly to ice-cold 20% fuming sulphuric acid (10.8 ml) taken in a round-bottomed flask with calcium chloride guard-tube and stirred when it dissolved completely. The reaction mixture was slowly warmed to room temperature, kept at room temperature for 30 min and then on steam bath for 5 h. The post-reaction mixture was poured in ice-water (20 ml) and aqueous ammonia solution was added to it slowly to decrease the acidity of the aqueous phase when the precipitation of the title compound became complete. After cooling thoroughly, the white mass was filtered, washed with cold water to get colourless crystalline solid, recrystallisable from ethanol, m.p. 270° (yield 2.21 g, 65.4%); ν_{max} 3100–3450 (br), 3120, 2940, 1720 (s), 1685 (s), 1585, 1480, 1460, 1435, 1380, 1260, 1220, 1190, 1080–1120 (s br), 930, 800, 730 (s); λ_{ma} (log ϵ) 314.5 (4.2), 297.0 (4.15), 229.0 (3.89), 216.5 (3.86) nm; λ_{min} (log ϵ) 301.0 (4.15), 256.5 (3.72), 218.5 (3.86), 214.0 (3.85) nm; δ_{H} 7.29 (2H, s, H-6, H-6'), 7.25 (2H, d, J 5.6 Hz, H-7, H-7'), 7.13 (2H, d, J 5.6 Hz, H-8, H-8'), 6.95 (2H, s, H-5, H-5'), 10.45 (br s, 3-OH, 3'-OH); δ_{C} 125.6 (d, C-7, C-7'), 121.91 (d, C-6, C-6'), 114.56 (d, C-8, C-8'), 112.56 (d, C-5, C-5'), 158.3 (s, C-2, C-2'), 148.3 (s, C-8a, C-8a'), 147.54 (s, C-3, C-3'), 141.67 (s, C-4, C-4'), 120.69 (s, C-4a, C-4a'); FAB-MS

(glycerol) 323 (M+1) (Found: C, 66.85; H 3.40. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_6$ requires: C, 67.08; H, 3.11%).

3,3'-Dihydroxy-4,4'-bi(benzo[b]pyran)-2,2'-dithione (**3**):

A mixture of 3,3'-dihydroxy-4,4'-bicoumarinyl (**2**) (3.0 g, 9.3 mmol) and Lawesson's reagent (6.0 g, 15 mmol) in toluene (50 ml) was heated under reflux for 2 h. Solvent was removed from the post-reaction mixture under reduced pressure and the residue was column chromatographed over silica gel. Title compound was eluted with chloroform-petrol mixture; white amorphous compound, recrystallisable from ethanol; m.p. 175° (yield 2.6 g, 80%); ν_{max} 3410 (br OH), 1600 (s), 1509, 1459, 1302.6, 1259.7, 1169.2 (s), 1078.5 (s), 1003.4 (s), 921.2 (s), 831.4, 660.0, 535.1 (s), 450.6; λ_{max} (log ϵ) 279.0 (3.22), 269.0 (3.92), 234.0 (4.18), 217.0 (3.95) nm; λ_{min} (log ϵ) 276.5 (3.22), 247.5 (3.01), 221.0 (3.95) nm; δ_{H} 7.60 and 7.58 (each 2H, each d, J ~6.9 Hz, H-7, H-7' and H-8, H-8'), 6.96 and 6.98 (each 2H, each s, H-5, H-5' and H-6, H-6'); δ_{C} 132.55 and 132.43 (each d, C-6, C-6' and C-7, C-7'), 113.72 and 113.57 (each d, C-5, C-5' and C-8, C-8'), 161.34 (s, C-2, C-2'), 126.58 (s, C-4, C-4'), 124.41 (s, C-4a, C-4a'); FAB-MS (*m*-nitrobenzyl alcohol matrix, NaCl) m/z 377 (M^+ + Na) (Found: C, 60.81; H, 2.98. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_4\text{S}_2$ requires: C, 61.02; H, 2.82%).

3,3'-Diamino-4,4'-bicoumarinyl (**5**):

Reaction of 3-aminocoumarin (**4**) (2.5 g, 15.52 mmol) with 20% fuming sulphuric acid (8.0 ml) was conducted in a way as above for 3,3'-dihydroxy-4,4'-bicoumarinyl (**2**) to get the title compound as pinkish white crystalline solid, recrystallisable from ethanol; m.p. >300° (yield 1.22 g, 49.1%); ν_{max} 3440 (NH_2), 1715 (s, C=O), 1650, 1595, 1565, 1465, 1410, 1340, 1235, 1180, 1130, 940, 900, 865, 785, 759 (s), 630; λ_{max} (log ϵ) 381 (3.21), 335 (4.02), 301 (3.87), 246.5 (4.06) nm; λ_{min} (log ϵ) 379.5 (1.93), 311 (3.77), 281 (3.64) nm; δ_{H} 6.72 (2H, s, H-5, H-5'), 7.61 (2H, d, J 1.9 Hz, H-6, H-6'), 7.42 (2H, dd, J 8.4 Hz, 1.9 Hz, H-7, H-7'), 7.19 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz, H-8, H-8'); δ_{C} 123.11 (d, C-7, C-7'), 122.00 (d, C-6, C-6'), 114.82 (d, C-8, C-8'), 107.92 (d, C-5, C-5'),

158.68 (s, C-2, C-2'), 147.79 (s, C-8a, C-8a'), 144.87 (s, C-3, C-3'), 134.01 (s, C-4, C-4'), 120.82 (s, C-4a, C-4a') (Found : C, 67.35, H, 3.97; N, 8.62. $C_{18}H_{12}O_4N_2$ requires : C, 67.50; H, 3.75; N, 8.75%).

Reaction of 3-aminocoumarin (4) with malic acid in 20% fuming sulphuric acid : Obtainment of fumaric acid N-(3-coumarinyl)- monoamide (6) : A mixture of 3-aminocoumarin (4) (2.5 g, 15.53 mmol) and malic acid (2.1 g, 15.7 mmol) was dissolved in 20% fuming sulphuric acid (8.0 ml) at 0° and the reaction mixture was slowly warmed to room temperature and kept at room temperature for 2 h and then its temperature was slowly increased to 95° and finally it was kept on steam bath for 6.5 h. The post-reaction mixture was then cooled to 0° and poured into ice-water mixture (20 ml); pH of the mixture was brought to ~9 with dropwise addition of aqueous ammonia. The mixture was cooled thoroughly in ice-bath. The residue was filtered, washed with ice-cold water (10 ml) and dried on steam bath and then triturated with chloroform (15 ml × 3) and filtered; the final residue was found identical with 5 after crystallisation from ethanol (yield 0.96 g, 38.6%). From the filtrate, chloroform was removed and the residue was recrystallised from chloroform-petrol mixture to get 6 as yellowish-white solid, m.p. 160° (yield 0.88 g, 21.7%).

Characterization of fumaric acid N-(3-coumarinyl)-monoamide (6) : ν_{\max} 3000–3460 (br s), 1730 (s), 1630 (s), 1585 (w), 1450, 1395, 1280 (s), 1230 (s), 1165 (s), 1130 (s), 1110 (s), 1025 (s), 900 (s), 840 (s), 765 (s), 670 (s), 615 (s); δ_H 5.82 (1H, d, *J* 13.2 Hz, NCO-CH=), 6.21 (1H, d, *J* 13.2 Hz, =CH-CO₂H), 8.70 (1H, s, H-4), 7.62 (1H, d, *J* 7.6 Hz, H-5), 7.43 (1H, t, *J* 7.6 Hz, H-7), 7.25–7.33 (2H, m, H-6, H-8); δ_C 139.54 (d, =CHCO₂H), 129.37 (d, =CHCON), 128.79 (d, C-5), 127.77 (d, C-7), 124.85 (d, C-6), 123.69 (d, C-4), 115.77 (d, C-8), 168.50 (s, CO₂H), 165.53 (s, CONH), 157.21 (s, C-2), 149.96 (s, C-8a), 125.75 (s, C-3), 119.93 (s, C-4a) (Found : C, 60.02; H, 3.76; N, 5.17. $C_{13}H_9O_5N$ give : C, 60.23; H, 3.47; N, 5.41%).

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References

- (a) A. I. Scott, *Quarter. Rev. (London)*, 1965, **19**, 1; (b) R. G. R. Bacon and A. R. Izzat, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, 791 and references cited therein.
- B. S. Furiness, A. J. Hannaford, P. W. G. Smith and A. R. Tatchell, in "Textbook of Organic Chemistry – A. I. Vogel", 5th ed., ELBS with Longman, 1989, p. 838.
- (a) A. R. Battersby, A. K. Bhatnagar, P. Hackett, C. W. Thornber and J. Staunton, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. I*, 1981, 2002; (b) P. L. Majumder and H. Kundu, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1984, **61**, 142; (c) T. Kametani, K. Fukumoto and M. Fujihara, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1971, 352; (d) D. H. R. Barton, A. M. Defflorin and O. E. Edward, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 530.
- M. J. S. Dewar and T. Nokaya, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **90**, 7134.
- P. L. Majumder and M. Basak, *Tetrahedron*, 1991, **47**, 8601.
- G. A. Olah, K. Dunne and Y. K. Mo, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1972, **94**, 7438.
- D. J. Cram and J. M. Cram, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1978, **11**, 8.
- (a) R. Nayori, I. Tomino, Y. Tanimoto and M. Nishizawa, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. I*, 1984, **106**, 709; (b) R. Nayori, I. Tomino, M. Yamada and M. Nishizawa, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. I*, 1984, **106**, 6717; (c) A. G. Olivero, B. Weidmann and D. Seebach, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1981, **64**, 2485; (d) W. Arnold, J. J. Daley, R. Imhof and E. Kyburz, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1983, **24**, 343.
- (a) J. Jacques and C. Fourquey, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1971, 4617; (b) E. P. Kyba, G. H. Gokel, F. de Jong, K. Koga, L. R. Sousa, M. G. Siegel, L. Kaplan, G. D. Sogah and D. J. Cram, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1977, **42**, 4173; (c) J. Brussee and A. C. A. Jansen, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1983, **24**, 3261.
- Y. Fujimoto, H. Iwadate and N. Ikekawa, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1985, 1333.
- K. Yamamoto, H. Fukushima, Y. Okamoto, K. Hateda and M. Nakesaki, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1984, 111.
- V. N. Dholakia and K. N. Tribedi, *Chem. Ind. (London)*, 1966, 160.
- S. Ray and S. Paul, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2004, **81**, 488.
- S. Scheibye, J. Krishtensen and S. D. Lawesson, *Tetrahedron*, 1979, **35**, 1339.
- B. Fernga and H. Wynberg, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1981, **46**, 2547.